

'the biggest, the best, the fastest', as a critique of the current state of design and consumerism. *The Fastest Clock in the World* gives digital time to a millionth of a second, *The Highest Popping Toaster in the World* brings an extra pop to breakfast with a compressed gas powered mechanism, *The Longest Lipstick in the World* provides a years worth of lip gloss in a yard long stick and *The Most Intricate Diary in the World* provides blank pages with lines for each minute of every hour.. Two designs from this series were the subject of short videos that were posted to YouTube.

The Fastest Clock in The World is a digital clock with hours, minutes, seconds, and six digits after the final decimal place. The aesthetic of the clock is minimal, referencing office and bedside alarm clocks of the 90's, with its 12 repeated red LED 7 segment displays. The final four digits of the clock move so fast that they appear not to be moving at all to the human eye. A discrete pause button on the top of the clock allows the user to pause the time to prove that the digits were actually moving - leaving the display showing the time 'it was' when they hit the button. The accuracy is faked, the last six digits displayed when the device is paused are random. The clock was designed to address the over-specification of so many of today's consumer electronics, whilst simultaneously questioning our work / life balance and the speed of modern life.

The Highest Popping Toaster in the World does exactly what its name suggests. It is a compressed CO2 powered toaster that set a new world record of 2.60m (ceiling height), at the Head Quarters of Guinness World Records (Glenday, 2009). The popping mechanism in toasters today is unnecessary, a result of cheap internal engineering and the more expensive toasters on the market having already discarded it. The first author was interested in how the toaster would be received, would people really want one? Would they think it was a complete waste of resources and an example of excessive consumer offerings?

Signs of Life, another of the first author's pieces that features on Youtube, appears to be a standard fire exit sign but is in fact a motion sensitive and

interactive animation. When people are present, the sign functions as a direction to the exit, but when the space appears to be empty the pictogram stretches, scratches and yawns before wandering out of the frame to take a break. The work is part of the permanent collection at the Museum of Modern Art in New York. Limited editions of the piece are also available for sale. The design originated from an exhibition that was held in a hotel, where the first author sympathised with the workers - the night porters, chamber maids and valets - more than the guests. The inspiration came when he noticed how many exit signs there were in the hotel with all of the characters balancing precariously on one leg, mid run, but going nowhere. He imagined these pictograms as the most overworked employees of the hotel.

While the aims of critical design and design for debate are valuable there is a danger that critical design preaches to the converted, that the debate is held within a very narrow demographic - students, gallery visitors, conference delegates and even that the actual designs may themselves ultimately be little more than commodities. The following sections of the paper focus on the reception of these pieces on YouTube.

METHODOLOGY

Recently web 2.0 sites such as YouTube which facilitate the distribution of user-generated content through videos and comments have been appropriated to assess the impact of new and emerging technologies. In order to exploit these resources in a rigorous way the second author and Paul Cairns have developed a methodological approach they characterise as "interdisciplinary analysis" (Blythe and Cairns 2009, Blythe and Cairns 2010 and Cairns and Blythe 2010). Interdisciplinary analysis includes "statistical modelling, content analysis, grounded theory and critical readings. In the following sections quantitative data such as viewing figures as well as qualitative data in comments to the videos are supplemented with perspectives drawn from critical theory to analyse the data (Ibid).

Such methods have been adapted to assess prototypes in an iterative design process (Constanzo *et al* 2010). Here web 2.0 sites were used to distribute open source software and instructions to assemble a Do It Yourself tangible user interface for a synthesiser and drum machine. Users then posted videos of their set up and compositions to YouTube and the feedback was used to improve the design. Rather than improve designs in an iterative process the aim here was to gauge responses to critical designs. The first author made short videos demonstrating the three designs and posted them to YouTube embedding the links in his own website. He also sought advice from PR specialists and distributed a press release, including High and low resolution images and the embed code for the video, to allow for easy blog posting.

The first author was trained as an industrial designer, and believes we want to associate ourselves with objects that pretend to make us better or fulfil our dreams, always offering us more. He has been influenced by the critical theories of Baudrillard, Eco and Lacan. His critical design is intended to explore the ways we consciously or unconsciously, allow ourselves to be told what we need and what will complete our sense of self as we see it in image form. But what did the YouTube and blogosphere audience make of his “excessive designs”? Placing videos of critical design on YouTube allows designers to test their intended meanings against viewer reactions. The following sections describe the video posts and responses. Comments are quoted as posted. The following sections on site statistics and qualitative data analysis (for a detailed discussion of method see Cairns and Blythe 2010).

SIGNS OF LIFE

The *Signs of Life* video begins with a shot of a fire exit sign on a wall, two people walk past and the camera closes in on the sign itself (see figure 1). Gradually, the stick figure pictured mid-run in the sign loses balance, stumbles and rights itself. It stretches, does some exercises and picks up the arrow sign folding it out into a table. It walks out of shot and then drags in a TV and sofa before sitting down to relax. Later he is joined by a stick figure in

a skirt, they turn the door on its side to make a bed and lie down. The stick figures hurriedly tidy everything away and the original sign pose is resumed. The camera pans out and a person walks past, the sequence then begins again.

Figure 1. Signs of Life

At the time of writing it had received 35,437 views.

Figure 2. YouTube viewing statistics for Signs of Life

It was embedded in a number of websites such as that of the first author, www.we-make-money-not-art.com, www.dezeen.com and www.designweek.co.uk.

Figure 3. Viewing Regions for Signs of Life

According to YouTube viewing figures the video was most popular amongst males between the ages of 35 and 44 although men in their forties and fifties (see figure 3). Judging from the site statistics it's impact on female YouTube viewers was negligible. It was

most popular in Germany, followed by Spain, Canada and the USA.

Although there were over thirty thousand views there were only nine comments. This may in part be because the video was being watched as an embedded video in other sites where comments were not possible. However it is a minority of visitors to a gallery that make comments in comment books so a minority response is perhaps to be expected. Three of the comments suggested that the video was interesting but too long and repetitive. For example, *“It was cool and smart but a bit too long”*. Similarly *“haha, that's very cool. I wish it was a bit shorter though, there were many bits that repeated themselves so I had to wiz it on every now and again.”* Two of the comments were simple statements of LOL (laugh out loud) amusement and approbation *“lol verry cool”* and *“ha ha simply brilliant”*. One comment expressed mild confusion *“Haha, I dunno whether or not to take that seriously”*. One comment joked: *“This guy is pretty bad at his job. If I were him, I would draw a picture of myself running. Then I could spend some quality time with my wife in that mystery room”*. This is interesting because it widens the conceit: if the figure is an employee then there must also be people making sure he does his job so he should draw a picture of himself to fool them.

The main responses then involved textual laughter *“haha”* and it seems that the work is for the most part appreciated and enjoyed; but one comment responds directly to the critique:

It's like a parody of all people who work: Working the whole day, then come home, watch TV and don't have any free time you can spend, 'cause you're too exhausted. It's always the same, it doesn't matter what or who you are...

This comment articulates quite explicitly the critical elements of this critical design. Despite living in an age of high tech labour saving devices none of us seem to have any free time, we are all exhausted, rest times have to be stolen back during the day.

Through this sort of comment we see clearly the message of the designer being understood and provoking thought, a satisfying and vindicating moment for a designer willing to share their work in a wider debating area.

FASTEST CLOCK IN THE WORLD

The video of the *Fastest Clock in the World* shows the clock in action with the last six digits flickering in a blur of movement as time passes (see figure 4). On two occasions a hand appears from the top of screen left and touches the device to stop the clock and show the display.

Figure 4. *Fastest Clock in the World*

At the time of writing it had been viewed 116,552 times.

Figure 5. YouTube stats for *fastest clock in the world*

Following its original embedded view there were a number of referrals from related videos and other websites that had embedded it including the first author's own site but mainly other design and technology websites. This video was particularly popular within existing 'tech' communities, with the

original posting coming from www.engaget.com one of the top ten technology blogs on the net.

Again the audience is overwhelmingly male but the spread of interest internationally is different to the previous video.

Audiences

This video is most popular with:

Gender	Age
Male	35-44
Male	45-54
Male	25-34

This video is most popular in:

Figure 6. Viewing Regions for fastest clock in the world

This video was most popular in China and Norway, then the USA and Russia (see figure 6). Again there were many more views than there were comments, just thirty four at the time of writing. A small number of these posts were the usual YouTube “LOL” type comments and one was a joke about a Casio wristwatch being faster than this stationary clock because it moves with the person who is wearing it. The majority of comments however were either technical or philosophical comments.

Several of the commentators guessed that the set up was a fake because the video showed the clock stopping with the last two digits on 9 both times the hand appeared. A chain of comments begins with someone saying the chances of this are slim, another suggests that the odds are one in a hundred, this is corrected and another viewer writes the following meta commentary on the exchange:

*“lol. six comments and 4 are about the first thing I thought of :)Of course the probability of any two specific pairs of digits appearing twice are 1/10,000 however the probability that in two stops, the last two digits are the same each time is 1/10,000 * 100 which is 1/1,000. More importantly, the chances that in two stops that the last two digits are different, is 999/1,000 suggesting that indeed, something is a little fishy.”*

This indicates quite a close viewing of the video and a serious if playful critique of the technical claims that are being made.

Many of the comments relating to technical issues questioned how such a device might work. One string of comments begins with a viewer asking if it was an atomic clock. This receives a flaming - “*how the fuck would it be atomic?*”. Others then speculate that it probably runs on a crystal “*like most clocks*”. One post defended the technical possibility of such a clock in some detail:

“This is possible... although not accurate. A crystal is most likely used in this circuit, and temperature will affect how precise the clock pulse from the crystal is. Propagation delay from how the circuit is designed will also cause the clock to 'lose' time. This clock is relatively simple to make using digital logic lpm counters. So there is nothing 'fishy' going on in the video. The clock would work great for beside the bed or timing a race, but it should be used for anything accurate.”

More interesting perhaps than these technical responses are those that dismiss the clock “*talk about redundant*” and those that raise philosophical as well as technical questions:

“Even so you're uC may be fast enough to calculate the accurate time, how do you manage to actually GET the exact time? What I mean: Unless you don't happen to sit in an atomic clock, there's basically no way to you can to get the _exact_ time after there's always some kind of technical delay time. And even those ain't exact. Anyway, ever thought about the fact that time is not real, it's just something mankind made up to measure the value of actions? Weeee!!!!... I like displays, nice work!”

This is perhaps the most direct engagement with the space that this critical design aims at. As with the other excessive design pieces it seeks to exaggerate current technological trends in a “*reductio ad*

absurdum” argument. This comment engages first with the technical problems of attempting to achieve such a display of time but then moves to a wider philosophical point: time is a human construct, a measure of our activity against some other regularly recurring phenomenon. Although the comments are perhaps atypical of most YouTubers to some extent the aim of creating debate with a design has been met here.

WORLD’S HIGHEST TOASTER

The video of the world’s highest toaster begins with a young woman wandering into a kitchen in her dressing gown. She puts two pieces of bread into the toaster, there is a time lapse and then the toast fires out at high speed, hitting the ceiling and making the woman flinch (see figure 7).

Figure 7. Screenshot from the world’s highest toaster

The moment of the toast firing out is then replayed in slow motion. The procedure is then repeated by a bearded ginger man who fires the toast into the corner of the room.

At the time of writing there were 150,717 views.

Figure 8. YouTube Stats for World’s Highest Toaster

A number of technology blogs such as gigazine and gizmodo embedded the video in their websites and brought new viewers. There were also links from the first author’s own website (see figure 8).

Figure 9. Viewing regions for World’s Highest Toaster

Again the video was most popular with males. Interestingly it was, again, not most popular in the country (or even the hemisphere) of origin but in South Korea and Japan (see figure 9). Clearly it is difficult to infer too much from this data and the popularity of a video in particular countries will depend in large part on the sites where it has been embedded. Nevertheless it is surprising that the video is far less popular in its country of origin than it is in Japan, indeed it’s popularity in led to the footage being used several times for Japanese TV shows, whilst its popularity in Germany led to interviews with the designer in both Der Spiegel and Der Standard, and a feature on a popular science show.

There were 41 comments to the video. Again many of the comments were LOLs and other YouTube colloquial expressions of approbation “Awesome”, “swееееет” “Damn!” and so on. Such comments are typical of any video enjoyed on YouTube and can be thought of as a form of audience feedback like textual applause (Blythe and Cairns, 2010). Many of these comments focussed on how funny the video was “PMSL” (i.e. pissing myself laughing) and “OMG that was hilarious”

A number of comments expressed a probably ironic desire to own one “WANT” and “where can I buy one?” and “that is some nice useless thing I want one”. Discounting for a moment “LOL” type comments, a desire to buy such a toaster was the most frequent response. “I would totally buy one for my friend and tell him to use it, scare the shit out of him.” This will be returned to in the discussion section of the paper.

There was no direct debate or comment on the critical intent of the design as with the World's Fastest Clock and to a lesser extent the Signs of Life video. It could be argued that the "laugh out loud" comments indicate that the video was appreciated as satire - a humorous but critical comment on our culture of excess. But this is not necessarily the case. The video and indeed the toaster itself, echoes non-satirical comedy such as that of Morecombe and Wise's classic breakfast sketch (see figure 10).

Figure 10. Still from Morecombe and Wise's breakfast sketch

Here two much loved 1970s British comedians dance around the kitchen to strip tease music, chopping melons with exaggerated speed and precision, tossing pancakes up to the roof and waiting an improbably long time for them to descend and catching toast as it flies out of the toaster all in time to the music. The incongruity of the precisely choreographed dance with the mundane activities of breakfast are funny without necessarily conveying any satirical or critical point. Similarly the girl in the video flinching clearly resonates with practical jokers who want to scare their friends.

Some of the comments were jokes "Meh. I just have a 5.25" bay in my computer that cooks my toast." In response to several comments about the toaster producing dusty toast someone wittily suggests buttering the ceiling. There were two negative YouTube comments "boring shit" and "fake" both received negative votes and were hidden from the comment list unless clicked on. Although negative and brief they are nevertheless contributions to a debate if only in garnering defensive responses. There was also one video response: "This is a Turbo Toaster". Here a man on a cherry picker catches a piece of toast fired from the ground from a similarly powerful appliance.

Figure 11 . "This is a Turbo Toaster" Screenshot

The two men then go on to make toast using a flame thrower because they want their toast "really toasted". Clearly this response was very much in a similar spirit to the "excessive design" series. The video ends with the toast being fired from the turbo toaster through a flame thrower and landing buttered on a table, echoing extreme sports type video posts. This then is excessive but not necessarily critical design.

Two of the three Yauner designs were featured on technology based sites like Gizmodo and Digg. These also generated comments and these were for the most part more acerbic than the YouTube comments. The following section considers comments on these other boards.

OTHER DISCUSSION BOARDS

There were nine comments for the *World's Highest Toaster* on Gizmodo. All of them were jokes of one kind or another. For instance "Screw that, is Tim Allen aware of this?" which references a macho DIY enthusiast sitcom character; or "this will go well with my highest popping rice cooker. I should really get that thing fixed" or "Needs giant bread to fall on someone or their car" (Gizmodo). One comment quotes the Simpsons di "Why do you mock me God? /That's not God that's a waffle stuck to the ceiling/ Mmm sacrilicious." Although nobody makes any critical comment about consumer society or continuing demands for bigger, better products the ironic tone of all of the comments indicates that gizmodo commentators got the joke.

There were seven comments following a Digg article on the Fastest Alarm Clock in the World. Again all of them were jokes. Some of them accepted the premise of the design and made jokes like "so you'd

be pissed if someone gave you a rolex?” and “Where were you yesterday at 5:45:37.583749 ???!?!”. Others were jokes that used the premise to make fun of non related subjects “... is the clock that they time lap dance music to at all strip clubs” and “It times how long it takes diggers to jack off to obama's picture”. Two comments involved themselves in technical discussions that distinguish between speed and accuracy “Fastness is a measure of speed and therefore a fast clock would show a second pass faster than an actual second for example”. This quote nicely combines pedantry and humour:

*“Ok, so everyone has already pointed out the fallacy of calling it “the fastest clock”, what's left for me? Do I ask if it has a radio? If it's a pain in the ass to program the alarm? How you re-set it correctly after the power goes out? s**t. That's what I get for showing up late”*

This response is interesting because it references a number of common usability problems and cultural gripes about alarm clocks. Through the popularity of this video a space has been created for the critical discussion of designed objects. It also indicates the pleasure that is taken in leaving comments - the ironic regret that someone had beaten him to pointing out fallacies.

Though the comments are few the evident humour and enjoyment indicate that online forums and the anonymity they provide may not only bring critical design to a wider audience but to a tougher crowd.

DISCUSSION

In answer to the first author’s original questions around the toaster: would people want to buy one, would they think it was a useless waste of resources, the answer, for some, was yes. They thought it was a useless waste of resources *and* they wanted to buy one. While comments about wanting to own the *World’s Highest Toaster* may be ironic it is not unusual for works of critical design to become commodities. The list of sales from the Phillips de Pury and Company for June 2006 indicate that Dunne and Raby’s compass table sold for 9,600 dollars.

Total Sold (including premium): \$ 1,767,485

Lot	Price	Lot	Price	Lot	Price	Lot	Price
201	102,000	259	26,400				
202	21,600	260	19,200				
203	84,000	261	8,400				
205	120,000	262	21,600				
206	15,925	263	48,000				
207	96,000	264	8,400				
208	84,000	267	6,000				
210	16,800	269	36,000				
211	66,000	272	9,600				
214	9,000	274	4,800				
217	9,600	277	14,400				
218	24,000	278	3,600				
219	9,000	281	18,000				
221	13,200						
223	7,200						
224	19,200						
225	2,400						
226	31,200						
227	9,600						
238	19,200						
240	45,600						
241	16,800						
244	1,200						
245	3,360						
246	9,600						
249	6,000						
250	24,000						
251	20,400						
252	50,400						
253	60,000						
254	15,600						
255	520,000						
258	10,200						

Figure 12. Compass Table Auction Figures

If the purpose of critical design is to make a point it is also to make money. Figure 12 shows auction sales figures for Dunne and Raby’s compass table. It should be no surprise that critical designs are also commodities. The books of radical social critics are commodities as well as critiques. But the meaning of Dunne and Raby’s Compass Table in the context of somebody’s collection of private possessions would be drastically different to the context of a gallery or a book about design practice. As an object in a private collector’s home it would perhaps still critically point up our unexamined relationships with electronic devices. But it would also signify the wealth and status of the owner. It would demonstrate not only what Bourdieu called cultural capital (Bourdieu 1986), in the sense of having the educational and intellectual capacity to appreciate such an object, but also plain old ordinary capital, in the sense of having enough money to buy it.

In the late nineteen sixties the artist and critic John Berger noted that all of the protesting art of that decade had been defeated in the same way as Duchamp and Bacon: it became, ultimately, a desirable possession and this was its tragedy:

“It cannot liberate itself. The more violent, the more extreme, the rawer it becomes, the more appeal it acquires as an unusual and rare possession” (Berger 2001: 105)

Few amongst us could afford to buy the Compass Table however much we enjoyed its critical role in drawing our attention to the magnetic fields generated by the increasing numbers of devices about our homes and persons. Perhaps then using YouTube as a platform for critical design is a worthwhile strategy in pursuing the critical design agenda. If critical design cannot escape becoming merely another commodity then perhaps videos about it are better vehicles for debate than the objects themselves?

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has argued that sites which allow for the creation and distribution of user generated content can expand the space of critical design. It described three critical designs and reported responses to videos about those designs on YouTube. Although there were few comments they indicated that at least some of the viewers had engaged in the debates that the designs were trying to provoke. The high viewing figures also suggested the potential of such sites for moving debates around critical design out of the academy to wider and more diverse circles. But perhaps critical design is inherently marginal?

A movement similar to critical design also exists in architecture. Architects like Bernard Tschumi see the role of architecture not as expressing an existing social structure but to question and revise it.

“Should we then make ordinary people uncomfortable and ill at ease in their buildings, just to impose on them the critico-ideological message that they live in an alienated, commodified and antagonistic society?” (Zizek, 2010)

Zizek and others doubt that there can be any direct “critical” architectural practice:

“However, our point is not that architecture *should* somehow be “critical”, but that it *cannot not* reflect and interact with social and ideological antagonisms” (Ibid)

Perhaps then to endorse a critical design practice, to produce “design for debate” or explicitly ideological design is to suggest a corollary of non-ideological design, innocent, or neutral design? This is not of course a position that Dunne or Raby or other critical designers would endorse.

But there is perhaps a more fundamental point to make about the space of critical design. In order for ideology to function there must be a space or gap between it and ourselves. Zizek has written extensively on the importance of jokes and irony in the operation of ideology:

“if there is an ideological experience at its purest, at its zero level, then it occurs the moment we adopt an attitude of ironic distance, laughing at the follies in which we are ready to believe - it is at this moment of liberating laughter, when we look down on the absurdity of our faith, that we become pure subjects of ideology, that ideology exerts its strongest hold over us” (Zizek 2010: 4)

For Zizek this is clear in military life as it is lived. Orders are obeyed but not unquestioningly, not without jokes, irony, satire, obscenity - otherwise how could the orders be obeyed? If we could not make fun of the ideology, if we could not laugh at it then we would have no choice but to believe it or rebel. For Zizek the formulation of a gap between the official line you are following and your true self, the self that sees through it, is essential for the ideology to function at all. It is difficult to imagine any relationship with the technologies we currently fetishise, the iPhone, the iPad if we were forced to take them entirely seriously, to give up our ironic distance, our critical perspective. Thus it is quite easy to conceive of a New York apartment full to the brim of the latest digital commodities and also the fastest clock in the world sitting on a compass table.

Conceptual art is often criticised as being solely an art of ideas. (Hughes 1991) It is claimed that it is not necessary to see the art itself, the idea can be communicated with a brief description of the work: a tent with the names of the artists' lovers written all

over it; a shark in formaldehyde; a head cast with the artists' blood. Those that have seen and appreciated the work may of course dispute this but it is a philosophy often embraced in critical design. It is not always necessary to actually make the artefact envisioned. Increasingly Dunne and Raby's critical designs are expressed in provocative scenarios. For instance, building on one of his student's projects, Dunne provocatively asks: if it is possible to grow meat then why would I not grow it out of my own cells and throw a dinner party where I serve the guests a piece of myself? It is not necessary to actually do this to question and debate the ethics of biotech. (Dunne, 2007). Similarly it is not necessary to make a clock accurate to the millionth of a second to question contemporary obsessions with efficiency and speed.

If critical design is primarily concerned with ideas then perhaps representations of critical design (such as videos) retain the force which can be compromised in the artefacts themselves. Like Bacon's painting no artefact of critical design could escape the defeat of becoming merely another desirable object. But digital representations of those artefacts such as YouTube videos can escape this deadlock. Like all digital representations the costs of replication are so close to zero that the collectable value of a video is nil. Whatever value a representation of a critical design has it is not economic. Perhaps then the space for critical design

is not around the objects themselves but in the new and emerging forums where they can be discussed.

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